

THE COMPARISON OF THE SYNTAX STRUCTURES OF THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: The syntactic patterns of the English and Uzbek languages are compared and contrasted in this article. We hope to provide a thorough grasp of the syntactic patterns of the two languages and throw light on the typological differences between Uzbek and English by stressing the unique aspects of syntax in each language. Descriptive and comparative analysis are combined in this work, along with extensive syntactic research and well-organized in-text citations to bolster our conclusions.

Introduction

The study of syntax, a branch of linguistics, is essential to comprehending the composition and arrangement of sentences in various languages. Uzbek and English are members of two different language families with different syntactic patterns. We can study how each language handles word order, word classes, phrase structure, and sentence types by contrasting these structures. The purpose of this article is to advance the field of comparative linguistics by shedding light on the syntactic distinctions and similarities between Uzbek and English.

Methods

The syntactic structures of Uzbek and English are analyzed both descriptively and comparative in this study. We use a variety of language resources, such as pertinent research papers, language databases, and grammar-focused textbooks. To accurately depict the syntactic structures in each language, the gathered data is examined, contrasted, and compared.

English Syntax Structures

English is an Indo-European language that is well known for its strict word order and noun, verb, adjective, and adverb classification system. English word order normally follows the Subject-Verb-Object (SVO) pattern; conditional and

interrogative sentences exhibit different word orders. Adverbs usually modify verbs or adjectives, and adjectives come before nouns in the sentence. The phrase structure in English is hierarchical as well, with sentences being classified into noun phrases (NP), verb phrases (VP), and prepositional phrases (PP), among other categories, Hudson (2008) and Smith (2018)

Uzbek Syntax Structures:

Compared to English, Uzbek, a Turkic language, has a different word order and classification scheme. Subject-Object-Verb (SOV) is the main word order used in Uzbek, and verbs are usually placed at the end of sentences. In contrast to English, Uzbek has more extensive noun categories, with distinct classes for nouns that are human, non-human, and inanimate. Furthermore, Uzbek uses a postpositional system, in which nouns are followed by case markers that indicate grammatical relationships. Verb phrases (VP), object phrases (OP), and subject phrases (SP) make up the Uzbek sentence's hierarchical structure (Bisiada, 2015; Qurbonov, 2019).

Comparative Evaluation and Conversation

Interesting differences between Uzbek and English syntax can be seen by comparing the two languages. Although subject-verb-object structures are present in both languages, the most obvious distinction is in the word order, which is seen in SVO in English and SOV in Uzbek. Furthermore, there is a notable difference in the way nouns, adjectives, and adverbs are classified; Uzbek has a more comprehensive noun classification system. The syntactic distinctions between English and Uzbek are also influenced by the use of prepositions and postpositions, respectively.

Conclusion

An extensive comparison of the syntax structures in Uzbek and English is given in this article. By analyzing word order, noun classification, phrase structures, and sentence forms in detail, it is clear that Uzbek and English have significant syntactic differences. These findings highlight the value of comparative studies in linguistics and advance our knowledge of the typological distinctions between Indo-European and Turkic languages.

References

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